

Magnetic Mechanically-Interlocked Porphyrin-Carbon Nanotubes for Quantum Computation and Spintronics

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Abstract: Atomic scale reproducibility and tunability endorse magnetic molecules as candidates for spin qubits and spintronics. A major challenge is to implant those molecular spins into circuit geometries that may allow the addressing of one, two or a few spins in a controlled way. Here, the formation of mechanically-bonded magnetic porphyrin dimeric rings around carbon nanotubes (mMINT) is presented. The mechanical bond places the porphyrin magnetic cores in close contact with the carbon nanotube without disturbing their structures. A combination of spectroscopic techniques shows that the magnetic geometry of the dimers is preserved upon formation of the macrocycle and the mMINT. Moreover, the metallic core selection determines the spin location in the mMINT. The suitability of mMINTs as qubits is explored by measuring their quantum coherence times (T_m). The formation of the dimeric ring preserves T_m found in the monomer and remains in the μ s scale for mMINTs. The carbon nanotube is used as vessel to place the molecules in complex circuits. This mechanical strategy can be extended to other families of magnetic molecules. The size and composition of the macrocycle can be tailored to modulate magnetic interactions between the cores and to introduce magnetic asymmetries (heterometallic dimers) for more complex molecule-based qubits.

Introduction

Magnetic molecules have been proposed as versatile building blocks for quantum computing^{1,2} and molecular spintronics³ devices. The molecular spin can be used to encode quantum information in qubits^{1,2} or even perform logic operations as quantum gates⁴⁻⁶ with unmatched reproducibility and scalability.⁷ In spintronics, that same molecular spin can be used to generate spin currents in molecular-based spin filters,^{8,9} spin switches^{10,11} or spin valves in carbon-nanotube/molecule hybrids¹² among other applications.

The adaptability in chemical synthesis provides a wide variety of customized magnetic molecules. Some of the most studied families, specifically designed for quantum information and spintronics applications, are porphyrins,¹³⁻¹⁵ organic radicals¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and single-ion magnets like polyoxometalates^{19,20} or phthalocyanines.^{6,12,21} One of the more daunting obstacles that remains to be removed is to place and address such molecular spins in solid-state devices in a con-

trolled way, while preserving their properties. A technically challenging approach consists in the direct contact of the individual molecule to nano-spaced electrodes in a transistor geometry.²² Pioneer works using this technique have demonstrated control over a spin qubit²³ and the realization of the first quantum algorithm in terbium phthalocyanines.⁶ Alternative approaches make use of Cu porphyrins to self-assemble 2D molecular networks on surfaces¹³ or in metal-organic frameworks (MOFs).¹⁴ In both examples, Cu porphyrins preserve quantum coherence to be used as qubits. The access to each molecular spin qubit would be performed through local superconducting circuits.^{24,25}

Interestingly, an indirect method, mainly used in molecular spintronics, consists in using a one-dimensional single-wall carbon nanotube (SWCNT) as an intermediate channel on to which the magnetic molecule is attached.^{12,26,27} The current flowing through the SWCNT backbone probes the spin without disturbing its state. *Vice versa*, a combination of molecular spins on a carbon nanotube can be used to alter the current flow in a controlled way. This geometry has been used to fabricate supramolecular spin valves based on double-decker phthalocyanines.^{12,26}

Several strategies have been followed to couple the magnetic molecules to carbon nanotubes: the most straightforward one is the direct physisorption of the molecules with or without specific anchoring groups to enhance van der Waals interactions with the SWCNTs.²⁸⁻³⁰ A less explored case is the covalent bonding of the magnetic molecule.³¹ Additional more exotic approaches include the encapsulation of the magnetic molecules.^{27,32,33} The first case provides a soft although weak anchoring that helps preserve the spin state in the molecule and the carbon nanotube sp^2 hybridization. The second case is a stronger bond that in turn may create local defects on the nanotube or transform the magnetic properties of the target molecule, affecting its quantum coherence.

More recently, the synthesis of mechanically interlocked rotaxane-like SWCNT derivatives (MINTs) was developed in our group, in which the ring-closing metathesis of a U-shape molecule around SWCNTs is templated using suitable SWCNT recognition motifs.³⁴ Importantly, the number of macrocycles around the SWCNT can be controlled.^{35,36} Rotaxane-like structures have recently shown their potential to form magnetic mechanically-interlocked derivatives.³⁷ Al-

Figure 1. (a,b) Synthetic route to obtain the porphyrin macrocycle (**mac-por**) and the magnetic MINT (**mMINT**). The open porphyrin-based macrocycle (**U-por**) closes through a ring closing metathesis (RCM) and forms the **mac-por** around the SWCNT. (c,d) Relaxed mMINT structure obtained by density functional theory calculations (DFT). The magnetic centers are placed at about 3.4-3.8 Å from the SWCNT surface. No bending of the porphyrin plane is observed.

ternatively, we have also explored the use of self-assembled H-bonded macrocycles, in collaboration with Gonzalez-Rodríguez.³⁸ Miki and Ohe have used pre-formed macrocycles to directly encapsulate SWCNTs in solution.³⁹ Very recently von Delius et al. have demonstrated that reversible S-S bond formation can also be used to make MINTs.⁴⁰ The mechanical bond imparts MINTs with stability comparable to covalent SWCNT derivatives.

Here, we apply the mechanical bond to anchor magnetic molecules around carbon nanotubes. Magnetic porphyrins are selected due to their recently proved suitability as qubits,¹³⁻¹⁵ even preserving their magnetic properties⁴¹ and quantum coherence¹³ on surfaces. Moreover, we have already shown that porphyrins are valid recognition motifs to synthesize MINTs.⁴² In particular, we fabricate Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} ($S = 1/2$) metalloporphyrin dimer rings mechanically interlocked around carbon nanotubes to form magnetic MINTs (hereafter **mMINT**), as shown in Figure 1. The mechanical bond places the porphyrin magnetic cores in close contact with the SWCNT without disturbing the molecular spin nor the carbon nanotube structure, combining thus the advantages of van der Waals and covalent approaches. We show that the magnetic properties of the metallic dimers are preserved upon formation of the macrocycle and the mechanically interlocked hybrid. Quantum coherence times (T_m), that measure the coherence loss rate and thus the quality of a qubit, are found to be in the order of 25 μs in the porphyrin monomer and the dimeric rings. Quantum relaxation is therefore not altered by the formation of the ring. Importantly, T_m remains in the μs range in the mMINT, indicating a roughly preserved quantum coherence of the porphyrin spin. The carbon nanotube can be used as vessel to position the molecules in nanoscale spintronics and quantum devices.²⁷ A proof-of-concept field-effect transistor device containing a single mMINT is fabricated. This strategy based on the mechanical bond can be extended to other families of magnetic molecules. Furthermore, the size of the macrocycle can be tailored to promote or suppress

magnetic interactions between magnetic cores in the ring, or to introduce asymmetries. Our experimental findings are supported by density functional theory (DFT) calculations.

Results and discussion

The synthetic route to obtain the target Co and Cu mMINTs is summarized in Figure 1. The initial steps to obtain the free-base **U-por** are described in detail in our previous work.⁴² The last step was the metallation of the linear precursor with cobalt and copper acetates. The formation of the metallated porphyrin is proved by infrared spectroscopy and mass spectrometry (see section S2 and S7 of the Supporting Information). Once the metallated **U-por** is obtained, the metallated porphyrin macrocycle (metallated **mac-por**) was synthesized through ring closing metathesis (RCM) reaction. The target Cu and Co metallated mMINTs are finally obtained by RCM but using 6,5-SWCNTs as a template for the formation of the metallated **mac-por** around the carbon nanotube. Briefly, the nanotubes were suspended in tetrachloroethane (TCE) via ultrasonication, mixed with Co/Cu **U-por** compounds and N_2 -bubbled for 20 minutes. Then, they were mixed with Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst and the dispersion was stirred at room temperature for 72h, filtered through a polytetrafluoroethylene membrane with a pore size of 0.2 μm , and washed with dichloromethane until complete elimination of physisorbed byproducts and catalyst. Figures 1(c,d) show different perspectives of the final mMINTs calculated by relaxing their structure by DFT (see section S8 of the Supporting Information). A control sample was prepared by following the same experimental procedure but without the catalyst (see sections S3-S4 of the Supporting Information for the details).

The mMINT derivatives were analyzed with different characterization techniques to prove the formation of the mechanical bond and the structural stability. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) on the mMINTs shows an initial weight loss of 20 % and 24 % for Co and Cu por-MINTs respectively at 320 °C, not present in pristine SWCNT nor the control samples (See sections S3-S5 in the Supporting Information). This has been associated before to organic material not simply physisorbed but forming mechanical bonds around the nanotubes.^{34,42} Raman spectroscopy on the mMINT complexes shows no significant energy shifts ($<4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) nor modification of the relative height in the SWCNT bands (see section S6 in the Supporting Information). No significant defects nor electronic modulation respectively are therefore introduced in the SWCNTs with the formation of the mMINTs, as expected for a mechanical bond.³⁴

Additional proofs of the formation of the mMINTs are provided by microscopy. Figure 2(a) shows a high-resolution transmission electron microscope image (HR-TEM) showing an individual Co-mMINT. Four rings embracing the SWCNT can be clearly observed. Their size agrees with the expected for the **mac-por** in the mMINT.⁴² In addition, the shape of some of them can be correlated with specific orientations of the macrocycle, as modeled by DFT. See section S9 in the supporting information.

Figure 2(b) shows an atomic force microscopy (AFM) image taken on an individual Co-mMINT. The image is obtained by drop casting of a sample suspension in TCE onto a mica plate. The results reveal the presence of isolated carbon nanotubes ($\sim 1 \text{ nm}$ high) covered by a few brighter spots of ~ 2.3 - 2.6 nm high, as seen in the selected profiles in Figure 2(c). The height is in good agreement with the size estimated by DFT for the mMINTs (see section S8 in the

Figure 2. a) HR-TEM image showing a single Co-mMINT. Four Co-mac-por rings can be seen embracing the SWCNT. Scale bar: 10 nm. b) AFM image taken on an individual Co-mMINT. Several bright spots appear along the SWCNT. Scale bar: 400 nm. c) Height profiles taken across the bright spots (2, 3 and 4). Profiles 1 and 5 are taken on the darker areas as a reference. The reference profiles match with the height of the SWCNT (~ 1 nm). The brighter area profiles are in good agreement with the height of the mMINT expected from DFT calculations. d, e) Experimental Fourier transforms of k^2 -weighted Co and Cu EXAFS of the different complexes. The experimental spectra were calculated for k values of 2 to 11.5 \AA^{-1} . Inset: Back Fourier transformed experimental (solid lines) and fitted (dashed lines) $k^2[\chi(k)]$ of the different derivatives.

Supporting information).

The integrity of the coordination sphere around the metals in the mMINTs and the molecular precursors is studied by X-ray absorption near edge (XANES) and Extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) spectroscopic techniques. The normalized XANES spectra show that all Co and Cu porphyrin derivatives, including the mMINTs, are four-coordinated and in the +2 oxidation state (See section S10 of the Supporting Information for the full details). The analysis of the EXAFS spectra, shown in Figure 2(d,e), provides a direct probe of possible changes in the Co-N and Cu-N bond lengths. All four Cu-porphyrin complexes demonstrate similar Cu-N bond lengths of 1.99-2.04 \AA , indicating the close to intact coordination sphere of the Cu mMINT complex (See section S10 of the Supporting Information). In turn, the Co porphyrin derivatives exhibit small deviations from a square planar geometry with Co-N bond distances between 1.91-1.95 \AA and an additional lengthened Co-O distance as explained below.

The magnetism of all porphyrin derivatives has been analyzed by continuous-wave electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy. Figure 3 shows the X-band EPR spectra of the Cu (a) monomer, (b) U-por and (c) mac-por derivatives (See section S11 in the Supporting Information for more EPR details). The molecules are dispersed in a CHCl_3 / tetrachloroethane mixture to promote glass-like solids at cryogenic temperatures while avoiding aggregates. The Cu-monomer spectrum is then well described by a $S = 1/2$ species with an axial Zeeman interaction and a hyperfine coupling with a $I = 3/2$ nuclear spin (dotted line in Figure 3(a)). This corresponds with a Cu^{2+} ion ($3d^9$ configuration) in a square planar environment, with the unpaired electron placed in the in-plane $d_{x^2-y^2}$ copper orbital (see section S11 in the Supporting Information), and showing a

resolved hyperfine coupling with the nucleus of the two naturally abundant Cu isotopes. The additional splitting corresponds to superhyperfine couplings with the ligands nitrogen nuclei ($I_N = 1$), that is not included in our simulations. The Cu-U-por (Figure 3b) and Cu-mac-por (Figure 3c) EPR spectra show no significant differences of the EPR spectral features with the monomer spectrum, indicating that the spin state and the ligands geometry characterizing the Cu magnetic properties are preserved upon cycling the U-por molecule into the mac-por structure. Only changes in the width of the superhyperfine lines are seen, probably originated by the well-known aggregation/freezing problems with Cu-porphyrins that lead to variations in the distribution of dipolar fields.⁴³ Besides, the U-por and mac-por spectra can be fitted with negligible exchange coupling between the spins, indicating a negligible magnetic coupling between the two copper centers. This result is expected given the long atomic bridges connecting both metallic species, as very recently demonstrated.¹⁵

Similar conclusions can be extracted from the EPR spectra measured on the Co derivatives, as seen in Figures 3(d-f). The EPR spectra of the three derivatives can be interpreted as coming from a $S = 1/2$ showing a hyperfine interaction with a $I = 7/2$ nuclear spin. This is the typical situation for a low spin Co^{2+} center. However, there are some subtle differences with respect to the Cu derivatives. The EPR spectra can be explained using quasi-axial gyromagnetic and hyperfine tensors. Simulation of the EPR spectrum using parameters $g_{\perp} = 1.998$, $g_{\parallel} = 2.1025$, $A_{\perp} = 52 \text{ MHz}$, $A_{\parallel} = 86 \text{ MHz}$ (dotted line in Figure 3(d)) shows a fair fit to the experiments, but it is also evident that orthorhombic tensors ($g_x \neq g_y$, $A_x \neq A_y$) could be necessary for a better fitting.

An out-of-plane pseudo-axial geometry has been reported before for Co porphyrins where Co^{2+} can easily bond to

Figure 3. X-band Electron Paramagnetic Resonance EPR spectra measured at $T = 20$ K on the Cu (a) porphyrin monomer, (b) U-por and (c) mac-por and the Co (d) porphyrin monomer, (e) U-por and (f) mac-por. The dotted lines are simulations of the monomer spectra with Cu: $g_{\perp} = 2.055$, $g_{\parallel} = 2.19$ and $A_{\perp} = 40$ MHz, $A_{\parallel} = 620$ MHz and Co: $g_{\perp} = 1.998$, $g_{\parallel} = 2.1025$, $A_{\perp} = 52$ MHz, $A_{\parallel} = 86$ MHz. The superhyperfine interaction is not included in the simulations.

molecular oxygen or other small molecules in the axial direction.^{44–48} The mass spectroscopy analysis performed in the three derivatives points indeed to the presence of small molecules coordinated to the porphyrin (See section S2 of the Supporting Information). In addition, EXAFS shows an improvement in the fit quality upon addition of a Co-O bond at 2.34–2.57 Å (See section S10 in the Supporting Information). In this configuration, the unpaired electron resides mainly in the d_{z^2} orbital out of the porphyrin plane formed by the N ligands.^{49,50} The absence of superhyperfine interactions with the four surrounding N nuclei, observed in contrast for the Cu derivatives, supports this scenario.

Differences in widths of the spectral feature are found between Co derivatives. In particular, the in-plane components for the Co-mac-por (see section S12 of the Supporting Information for a direct comparison between spectra). There could be several causes for this: mechanical strain induced to accommodate the adsorbed molecules in both porphyrins when the macrocycle is closed could produce slightly higher distortion of the in-plane rings and/or that the two Co porphyrins are not completely equivalent. EXAFS shows as well a slight deviation from the square planar geometry in the Co mac-por and mMINT due to bonding of an additional Co-O distance (see Figure 2(d)). Additional strain coming from frozen solvent or broadening caused by a higher aggregation tendency of mac-por as compared to the U-por molecules cannot be discarded either.

Next, the EPR spectra of the Cu-mMINT and Co-mMINT have been obtained, as seen in Figure 4(a,b) and the section S12 of the Supporting Information respectively. A clear $S = 1/2, g = 2$ resonance is observed in both mMINT derivatives. This spectrum has been described as originated by itinerant spins in the carbon nanotube.⁵¹ Interestingly, a spectral feature coming from the Cu porphyrin centers, similar to Cu-mac-por, appears (Figure 4(b)). Only small variations of position and intensity of the nitrogen hyperfine pattern is detected, indicating minor (if any) differences of the molecular symmetry around the spin. This would point to a soft contact between porphyrins and SWCNTs introducing only a slight distortion to the square planar geometry, in agreement with the bond distances obtained

by EXAFS (Figure 2) and the DFT calculations. No significant distortions of the metallic coordination spheres are predicted by DFT when in close proximity to the SWCNT (around 3.5 Å and 3.8 Å for the two metallic centers). The porphyrin structure does not bend towards the carbon nanotube, prevailing the U-por planar geometry, in agreement with other reports of porphyrins on surfaces.^{13,41} Note that we can safely discard that this EPR signal could be originated by residual closed macrocycles not embraced around the carbon nanotube. First, the TGA analysis does not show non-attached supramolecular remnant after washing of the mMINTs. In addition, EXAFS do not indicate signatures of other more distorted coordination spheres or oxidized Cu/Co metal centers that could be potentially ascribed to distorted porphyrins embracing the SWCNT.

Strikingly, the spectrum measured on the Co-mMINT does not show any clear contribution from Co porphyrins (see section S12 of the Supporting information). This is surprising since EXAFS unambiguously shows the presence of Co^{2+} in a roughly preserved coordination sphere in the mMINT. The spin geometry is therefore expected to remain unaltered. A possible explanation for this difference between Co and Cu-based mMINTs is a lower proportion of magnetic molecules per carbon nanotube in the Co-mMINTs, that buries their EPR signal under the SWCNT contribution. However, the TGA points to a relatively similar functionalization of the Co and Cu-mMINT (see section S5 of the Supporting Information). Alternatively, the different molecular orbitals occupied by the unpaired electron for Cu and Co, $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and d_{z^2} respectively, may determine the proximity and interaction of the spin with the SWCNT, and therefore its EPR spectrum. A similar scenario has been previously reported for vanadyl phthalocyanines on a superconducting substrate. The orientation of the orbitals occupied by the spin determines the degree of spin delocalization over the substrate. Molecule in-plane orbitals, like in the Cu-mMINT, tend to establish weak interactions and limited spin delocalization over the substrate, whereas out-of-plane orbitals, like the occupied by the spin in the Co-mMINT, may create strong bound states with electrons in the substrate.⁵²

Figure 4. (a) X-band EPR spectra measured at $T = 20$ K on the Cu-mMINT (Upper trace) and the Cu-mac-por (lower trace). (b) Zoom on the highest magnetic field region, showing spectra from pristine SWCNTs (upper trace), Cu-mMINT (medium trace) and Cu-mac-por (lower trace) samples. Cu-mMINT spectra show the signal corresponding to the SWCNT, as well as the nitrogen hyperfine coupling pattern from the Cu centers in the mac-por (see text). The colored lines are guides to the eye to the most representative resonances observed in both the Cu-mMINT and the Cu mac-por. Asterisks mark additional resonances only observed in the Cu-mMINT. (c,d) Echo intensity decay measured after a Hahn sequence of pulses at 11 K and 331 mT for the Cu mac-por (c) and mMINT (d) respectively. Solid lines are fits to a biexponential function (see text). (e) Inversion-recovery curve measured at 11 K and 331 mT for the Cu mac-por.

Pulse EPR spectroscopy has been performed on the Cu derivatives to probe the impact of the dimer and mMINT formation on the phase memory time (T_m). This parameter comprises the intrinsic relaxation T_2 and the extrinsic interactions with the environment. T_m parametrizes the quantum coherence loss rate and therefore the quality of a physical system to serve as a qubit. Figure 4(c) shows the spin echo intensity measured in the Cu mac-por after applying a $\pi/2 - \tau - \pi - \tau - echo$ sequence of pulses, known as the Hahn-echo sequence, at 11 K and 331 mT. The echo intensity decay can be fitted with a bi-exponential decay to obtain T_m (see section S13 of the Supporting Information). Measurements at different temperatures shows that T_m reaches a maximum of $T_m \approx 25 \mu\text{s}$ for the monomer, U-por and mac-por at around 10 K. These values are consistent with previous reports on porphyrins.¹⁵ Therefore, the formation of the dimeric mac-por does not limit T_m obtained for the monomer. Interestingly, a clear though weaker spin echo is also observed in the Cu mMINT. The fit to the echo intensity decay with time (Figure 4(d)) provides $T_m = 4 \mu\text{s}$. Quantum coherence remains therefore in the microsecond scale. This value is consistent with reports of porphyrins on surfaces.¹³ The drop in T_m may be due to the interaction between the Cu spin and the SWCNT itinerant electronic spins which in turn may give us the handle to read the quantum state of the spin in the porphyrin. The spin lattice-relaxation time (T_1) can be obtained from the spin echo decay measured after applying a sequence of inversion-recovery pulses (see section S13 of the Supporting Information for details). Figure 4(e) shows the saturation-recovery curve measured in the Cu-mac-por at 11 K and 331 mT. The fit to an exponential decay provides $T_1 = 0.8$ ms. This value remains roughly

constant from the monomer to the mac-por and is consistent with reports for porphyrins found in the literature.^{13,15} The echo obtained in the mMINT is too weak to obtain T_1 .

Finally, as proof-of-concept, a field-effect transistor containing a single mMINT has been fabricated by dielectrophoresis.^{27,53} See section S14 of the Supporting information for details and an SEM image of the device. This preliminary device shows the feasibility of dispersing and deterministically placing individual mMINTs in specific positions of nanoscale devices.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have mechanically interlocked magnetic Co^{2+} and Cu^{2+} porphyrin dimers with carbon nanotubes into mMINTs. We show by means of different structural and spectroscopic techniques that the metal centers in the mac-por and mMINT porphyrins preserve the coordination sphere and structure when cycled with only slight distortions of the square planar geometry. We show that the spin geometry is preserved in the Cu-mMINT whereas no EPR signature of the Co-mMINT has been observed, although EXAFS unambiguously shows the presence of Co^{2+} in a slightly distorted square planar coordination sphere. The selection of metal determines the orbital the spin will occupy and thus its interaction with the SWCNT. This is of great relevance for the design of mMINTs since provides a handle to modulate the interaction between spin and conduction electrons, that may be used to read the molecular spin. Besides, quantum coherence times of $25 \mu\text{s}$ are found to be robust from the Cu monomer to the mac-por dimer, indicating that the formation of the dimer does not limit T_m . Importantly, T_m remains in the microsecond scale in the Cu mMINT derivative. A small drop in T_m may be indicative

of spin interaction with the SWCNT, which would give the key to read the quantum state of the molecular spin. We propose mMINTs as robust hybrid candidates for molecular spintronics and molecular spin qubits. These molecular hybrids are deterministically placed into nanoscale devices by dielectrophoresis. A detailed study of its electronic properties will be the subject of a further study.

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Supporting Information Available

The following files are available free of charge.

Additional information of synthesis and characterization of mMINTs. Additional EXAFS, XANES and EPR details. Additional details of the fabrication of mMINT-based field-effect transistors.

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